

ACTIVE METHODS OF EFL TEACHING IN NUMEROUS GROUPS OF STUDENTS

Ruzimova Zaynab Egamberganovna

A postgraduate student of MA at UzSWLU

Novik Kseniya Pavlovna

Teacher of the Department "Applied Sciences of the English language"

Uzbekistan State University Of World Languages

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Annotation. Today, innovative pedagogical technologies are considered as the most effective tools in the educational process. They are widely used in World foreign language teaching practice. Not all active teaching methods fall into Ham interactive methods. When we say interactive teaching methods, first of all, the way in which we learn and master the topic among students is based on mutual communication. This article discusses the use of interactive techniques in English lessons.

Keywords: English teaching, interactive teaching, interactive methods

INTRODUCTION

It is known that in studies carried out in the methodology of teaching a foreign language, interactive methods have been shown to have a higher level of efficiency compared to traditional methods. When English classes are organized on the basis of interactive methods, students think freely independently, education is student-teacher, and student-student cooperation is carried out. Interactive is the most active educational method, providing learners with the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies, such as effective exposure in the quick term, independent thinking, work on themselves, critical thinking, creativity. The interactive lesson is based on the interaction of students.

The term interactive in English means "interactive," interact, i.e., inter means "mutual," Act " means action, influence, activity. Interactivity is the activity of two people between them. That is, the educational process is carried out as a mutual conversation, in a dialogue form or on the basis of teacher-student interaction. Interactivity occurs in interactivity, action, interaction, student-teacher, student-student (Subject-subject) conversations.

The main goal of interactive methods is to create an environment in which the most favorable environment for the educational process is to create a situation, creating an environment for the active, free, creative thinking of the student, employing his needs, interests, internal capabilities. In the process, not a single student will be left out and have the opportunity to openly express the feedback they hear, read, see. The process of mutual exchange of ideas takes place. In students, enthusiasm for learning, interest increases, and mutual friendly relations are formed. Interactive techniques will help improve the effectiveness of English lessons. The main criteria for interactive education are as follows:

- holding informal discussions;
- the possibility of freely stating and expressing educational material;
- low number of lectures;
- high number of seminars;

- creating opportunities for students to take the initiative;
- give assignments to work as a small group, large group, class team;
- written work consists of performance and other methods, which have a special significance in improving the effectiveness of educational work.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In many literature, it is noted that currently the most popular interactive educational methods are "Keys-stadi" (or "study keys"), "Blist-survey", "modeling", "creative work", "problem education". Interactive educational strategies reported include "Mind attack", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Zinamazina", "host", "Rotastia", "rounded snow" styles. The approach to the organization of group work in the separation of interactive educational strategies from the content of interactive educational methods is based, in a certain sense, on the comparison of the strategy. In fact, these strategies also belong more to interactive educational methods, among which there are no other differences. Interactive graphic organelles: "fish skeleton", "BBB", "conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "t-table", "Insert", "cluster", " why?" , "How?"and b. When distinguishing interactive graphic organizers, the main points in such training are based on the fact that they are expressed in writing in different graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers also applies more to interactive educational methods.

The main goals of interactive methods are:

- raising the interest of students in the process of mastering the subject of English;
- bringing teacher activity in English closer to real life conditions;
- effective communication methods, that is, the correct formation of teacher-student and mutual, communication skills;
- raising the process of mastering new theoretical knowledge and practical skills to a new level;
- increase the responsibility of students to the educational process.

From traditional methods of teaching, such as interactive methods, explanation, instruction and the use of tools, its effectiveness is high, which is an important factor in the formation of students as individuals, increasing their private abilities, ensuring their creative independence.

Interactive education and traditional education are different from each other:

1. It is necessary to take into account the feasibility of organizing interactive classes on topics in the curriculum. This involves the use of interactive or traditional types of training, which ensure the full achievement of the goal of training on each topic.

2. In order for an interactive session to be effective, it is necessary to ensure that students know the basic concepts and preliminary information on its subject before the new session.

3. In an interactive session, it is necessary to take into account that in order for students to work independently, a lot of time is spent compared to a traditional one. It is important for students to formulate speech skills such as listening, speaking, writing and reading through interactive techniques, and in a moving communicative environment it is important to engage students in language learning during the course of the lesson, to guide students to the targeted use of English, and to encourage natural speech. Below we bring brief

information about some of the techniques designed to provide interactivity between students in English lessons:

KWL-I knew, I want to know, I know.

What I knew	What I want to know	What I learned

In the teaching of foreign languages, this graph is widely used from the organizer. It can be used for the purpose of identifying what students know and want to know from the beginning of the lesson on the topic being passed by filling in columns 1 and 2. At the end of the lesson, column 3 is completed by students.

PPP-presentation, practice and production

Presentation, Practice, Production (PPP)

This method allows readers to get acquainted with a new topic. By completing the thematic assignments provided by the teacher, in the next invasion, students use English in a creative way, such as creating scripts themselves.

ESA-Engage, Study and Activate (Training, Learning, and activation) will focus on improving the skills of verbal communication in English by working in pairs and groups. For example, students are offered to continue the unfinished sentence with the necessary words by mutual agreement in order to work in a pair. In this process, the English language develops independent thinking, self-confidence, communication skills.

Case Study-involves collecting information on the proposed topic. Each participant gets acquainted with the list of questions and assignments. The teacher helps to formulate questions and answers, it is ensured that mutual communication is carried out in English.

Logical sequence method-according to the logical sequence method, students first listen to dialogues, then read the text, and then watch a short video in English and develop skills such as practicing.

Role-play is a role-playing game that simultaneously performs speech, play, and educational activities. Students play a variety of roles in English. The goal of the role-playing game is to form and develop students ' speech skills. Since role-playing games are based on interpersonal relationships, it is the national curriculum project of general secondary education that creates the need for dialogue, with an interest in participation in a foreign language. Performs a motivational and stimulating function and allows you to imitate the communication of students in various speech situations.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the teacher, aiming to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson, achieves his goal only if he skillfully uses interactive lesson methods in his place. Pedagogical technology is organized in its essence with the help of forms, methods and tools, increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and determining mutual cooperation between the teacher. In addition, it ensures the acquisition of thorough knowledge of the subjects of study by students. forms independent, free and creative thinking skills in students. And the necessary conditions are created for students to realize their potential. It is also necessary to guarantee the achievement of the primacy of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process..

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